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Effect of Linear-Power-Point Instruction on Performance in Trigonometry Concepts among Senior Secondary School Mathematics Students in Katsina State, Nigeria

Sabo, Abubakar¹

abusabokguga@gmail.com, asabo@fudutsinma.edu.ng
Tel: 08039498636

Kankia, Dalhat Aminu¹

adalhat@fudutsinma.edu.ng

^{1,2}Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State.

Abstract

This study aimed to assess effect of Linear-Power-Point Instruction on Performance in Trigonometry concepts among senior secondary school Mathematics students in Katsina State, Nigeria. The research design of this study is quasi-experimental design. The population is made up of 69932 (41196 males and 28736 females) senior secondary school class two (SS II) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina state. A sample of 199 SSII students (Male 123 and Female 76) was chosen through a multistage sampling technique. One instrument, the Trigonometry Performance Test used to gather data for the study. This instrument was validated by experts and after pilot testing, demonstrated high reliability with estimates of 0.83. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation was utilized to answer the research questions, while t-test was employed to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study indicated that there was a statistically significant difference in the mean performance scores of the students taught using Linear PowerPoint group and non-digital technology groups. Based on these findings, it was recommended that Linear PowerPoint Instructional packages should be encouraged in schools for teaching Trigonometry.

Keywords: Linear Power Point, Non-digital technology, Teaching Strategies

Introduction

The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education has significantly transformed teaching methodologies, particularly in the domain of mathematics. Among the various ICT tools, PowerPoint presentations have emerged as a pivotal resource for educators. PowerPoint, a widely utilized presentation software, offers a dynamic and interactive platform for disseminating information, thereby enhancing the teaching and learning experience. Nigeria government in her National Policy on Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in Education boldly expressed the impossibility of qualitative education in 21st-century without integration of ICT into education (FGN, 2019).

PowerPoint is a standard part of the Microsoft Office software package which is used for preparing a sequence of slides that are displayed to the audience on a computer guided monitor. Presentation developed with this type of software can be saved digitally and easily modified, facilitating future use. Microsoft PowerPoint allows teachers to include chart clip, art photographs, sound or video segments to demonstrate concepts (Effiong & Ekpo-eloma, 2016; Marcovitz 2021). The above description portrait linear format of PowerPoint that is, each slide is designed to proceed one slide right after another. The first slide transits to the second, which transit to the third, and so forth (Garth, 2021). The traditional PowerPoint presentation is known as a “slide show” which includes a series of screens presented one after another.

Fig. 1 illustration of Linear Power Point

The utilization of linear PowerPoint presentations can substantially empower teachers by providing a structured and visually engaging medium for content delivery. This approach facilitates the incorporation of multimedia elements such as images, videos, and animations, which can elucidate complex mathematical concepts and cater to diverse learning styles. By leveraging these features, educators can create more engaging and effective instructional materials (Mensah & Nabie, 2021). Empirical research underscores the efficacy of PowerPoint in enhancing mathematics performance. For instance, a study by Mensah and Nabie (2021) demonstrated that students instructed via PowerPoint presentations exhibited higher achievement

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and motivation compared to those taught through traditional methods. The visual nature of PowerPoint aids in sustaining student interest and engagement, which are critical for effective learning. Furthermore, the adaptability of PowerPoint presentations allows educators to tailor their lessons to the specific needs of their students, thereby fostering a more personalized learning environment. Linear PowerPoint presentation remained the most commonly integrated DPT in the classroom. Linear PowerPoint is a pattern of PowerPoint slide design that proceed one slide right after another. The sheer popularity of this presentation tool comes from the belief that representation of information using auditory and visual inputs improves learning (Mayer & Moreno, 2017).

Linear PowerPoint is said to be very effective in drawing and maintaining students’ attention and this is reported to have a positive impact on students’ academic performance and motivation (Erdemir, 2014; Savoy, Proctor & Salvendy, 2014; Wofford, 2014). Linear PowerPoint appeals to sight and hearing which are the most used senses in teaching and learning activities (Gambari, Zubairu, Daramola, Abubakar, & Tukura. 2018). This mode of technology integration, however, is a semi-compromised 21st-century learning environment. The learners only received information presented by the teacher through digital technologies but they are not actually using digital technology to construct knowledge. The suitability of Linear PowerPoint, therefore, for digital natives (21st-century learners) has been questioned because the issue of students using previous knowledge to construct new knowledge through interaction with learning content is restricted (Chen, 2021).

Research reports reveals that most science teachers use the lecture method in teaching Mathematics. The method does not enhance students’ academic performance especially in the acquisition of process skills as Olariwaju, (2019) opined that, lecture method is defective because it involves verbal presentation of pre-planned lesson to the students which requires little or no instructional aid and so does not promote students’ higher level of thinking.

Lecture method according to Adeyemi (2018) is a teaching approach that entails verbal presentation of scientific facts, concepts and principles to learners. During lecture, teacher focuses the students’ attention on the key points in the lesson and may use diagrams or other representations to elaborate on the subject matter. A neglected variable in the teaching and learning of Mathematics is the students’ learning abilities Garba, (2022). The objectives of Mathematics teachers are to identify the ability of students in their classroom and device teaching strategies that could best carry along the entire class during lesson. Hence, the need for a strategy that will ease the way teacher teaches is important through integrating technology into teaching and learning, example; linear PowerPoint and so on.

Figure 2
Theoretical Framework

Knowledge Transmission theorist see learners as “sponge” considered to be empty vessels, blank slates, or passive observers. The assumption has been that if teachers speak clearly and students are motivated, learning will occur. If students do not learn it is because they are not paying attention or they do not care. These ideas were grounded in theories of learning that focused on behavior. One behavior leads to another, behavioral-learning theorists argued, and so if teachers act in a certain way, students will likewise act in a certain way. According to Gagne and Medsker (1996) in Fakomologbon (2016), “behaviorist

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theories assumed that learning could be studied and facilitated by manipulating only the external environment of the learner, observing the learner's overt behaviour and managing the external consequences of that behavior.

The theory is relevance to the present study in diverse ways. First of all, the teaching and learning environment in Nigeria school only compliance with behaviorist theories of what teacher and students do in teaching and learning process. Teacher present the topic and convince learner that that is the fact and they must master it in order to pass examination. This fact is also presented in non-digital technology that supported them such as maps, textbook chalkboard among others. This method has recorded a great success as it has recorded same great failure, (Adegoke, 2017). What success then can be ascribed to it, is it in knowledge acquisition or knowledge application? On the other hand, the theory is inadequate for the present study. The theory is based on operant conditioning and classical conditioning whose principles give insufficient opportunities for student to construct their own learning (Wilson & Peterson, 2015).

The dual coding theory proposed by Paivio attempts to give equal weight to verbal and non-verbal processing. Paivio (1986) in Paivio (2015) expressed that human cognition is unique in that it has become specialized for dealing simultaneously with language and with nonverbal objects and events. Moreover, the language system is peculiar in that it deals directly with linguistic input and output (in the form of speech or writing) while at the same time serving a symbolic function with respect to nonverbal objects, events, and behaviors. Any representational theory must accommodate this dual functionality. The main principle of the theory is that recall/recognition is enhanced by resenting information in both visual and verbal form. The theory assumes that there are two cognitive subsystems, one specialized for the representation and processing of nonverbal objects/events (i.e., imagery), and the other specialized for dealing with language (Kearsley, 2017). Paivio also postulates two different types of representational units: "imagens" for mental images and "logogens" for verbal entities which he describes as being similar to "chunks" as described by Miller. The use of linear PowerPoint presentations can significantly enhance the teaching and learning of mathematics. By empowering educators with effective strategies and tools, it is possible to improve student performance and foster a deeper understanding of mathematical and particularly Trigonometry concepts. However, it is crucial to use these tools judiciously and provide educators with the necessary training and support to ensure their successful implementation.

Statement of the Research Problem

The researchers' observed that the teaching and learning of Trigonometry like any other subjects in Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina State is still characterized by integration of non-digital technology and teacher-centered learning approaches even in the schools that have adequate digital technology at their disposal. This observation is in line with the report of Yusuf (2022) who reported that teachers in Katsina State as a whole are not ready to integrate digital technologies in teaching and learning even when these technologies are readily available. It is worth to note that Mathematics teachers' loyalty to non-digital technology integration and its corresponding teacher-centered teaching and learning approaches do not result into the desired Trigonometry learning outcomes in both affective and cognitive in Katsina State. Udoh (2011) reported that, many students find it difficult to solve mathematical problems among which is the trigonometric problem which no doubt constitutes an educational problem with serious implication. Unfortunately, despite all the relative importance of mathematics in science and other field of studies, students' performance in the subject has remained constantly poor (Adolphus, 2011).

However, WASSCE Mathematics Chief Examiners' Reports (2015-2023) reported that questions on trigonometry were poorly attempted by the candidates which contribute toward poor performance of students in mathematics in general. In an attempt to possibly promote the performance and equally solve the problems of poor performance and ability of students in trigonometry in particular and mathematics in general, technology integration using linear power point is proposed to investigate its combining significant effect from which predictions about the performance of students was made to see if it could address this problem or not. This research intended to lurch a war against the use of non-digital technology to teaching mathematics in large classes at secondary schools. And also, a war for the implementation of the use of Linear Power Point technology to teach mathematics topics particularly Trigonometry.

Objectives of the study

The Objectives of the study were to;

1. Determine the mean performance score of students taught the concept trigonometry using linear-power-point strategy and those exposed to non-digital technology in Katsina State.
2. Examine the mean performance score of male and female students taught the concept trigonometry using linear-power-point strategy in Katsina State

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Research Questions

The following questions guided the study;

1. What is the mean performance score of students taught the concept trigonometry using linear-power-point strategy and those exposed to non-digital technology in Katsina State?
2. What is the mean performance score of male and female students taught the concept trigonometry using linear-power-point strategy in Katsina State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught trigonometry using linear power point and those taught using non-digital technology in Katsina State;
2. There is no significant difference between mean performance of male and female students taught trigonometry using linear power point in Katsina State

Methodology

The design adapted for this study is the quasi-experimental design specifically, pretest, posttest, non-randomized, and nonequivalent control group design. The population of the study consists of 69932(41196 males and females) senior secondary school class two (SS II) students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Katsina state. A sample of 199 SSII students (Male 123 and Female 76) was chosen through a multistage sampling technique. The Trigonometry Performance Test used to gather data for the study. This instrument was validated by experts and after pilot testing, demonstrated high reliability with estimates of 0.83.

Presentation of Result

Research Question 1 and hypothesis 1

H₀₁ There is no significant difference between the mean performance of students taught trigonometry using linear power point and those taught using non-digital technology in Katsina state.

Table 1

T-test analysis showing difference between the mean performance of students taught trigonometry using linear power point and those taught using non-digital technology.

Group	N	Mean	Std. D.	t-cal	DF	P-value
Linear Power Point	110	47.6545	20.02725	4.209	197	0.028
Non digital Technology	89	26.3820	17.11625			

(Field work, 2024)

The above table revealed that the mean performance students taught using Linear Power Point is (47.6545) with Standard Deviation of 20.02725 and the mean performance of students taught using Non digital Technology is (26.3820) with Standard Deviation of 17.11625. The difference in the mean performance was (11.2725). Also, the table showed that the t-cal value is (4.209) and P-value value is (0.028) which is less than the alpha value (0.05). Hence, the null hypothesis of the research was rejected and implied that there is significant difference between the mean performance of students taught trigonometry using linear power point and those taught using non-digital technology.

Research Question 2 and hypothesis 2

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between mean performance of male and female students taught trigonometry using linear power point in Katsina State

Table 2

T-test analysis showing difference between the mean performance of male and female taught trigonometry using linear power point and those taught using non-digital technology.

Sex	N	Mean	Std. D.	t-cal	DF	P-value
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Male	123	43.9837	16.96959	1.259	197	.000
Female	76	40.3947	23.09810			

(Field work, 2024)

The above table revealed that the mean performance of male taught using Linear Power Point is (43.9837) with Standard Deviation of 16.96959 and the mean performance of female taught using Non digital Technology is (40.3947) with Standard Deviation of 23.09810. The difference in the mean performance was (3.589). Also, the table showed that the t-cal value is (1.259) and P-value value is (.000) which is less than the alpha value (0.05). Hence, the null hypothesis of the research was rejected and implied that there is no significant difference between mean performance of male and female students taught trigonometry using linear power point and those taught using non-digital technology.

Discussion of Findings

This study established that there was a statistically significant difference in the mean performance scores of the students taught using Linear PowerPoint group and non-digital technology groups. The finding of the present study is in line with Adeniran, Laolu, and Ayotola (2016), Effiong and Ekpo (2016), Falode, Ojoye, Ilobeneke, Falode (2016), Gambari, Yusuf and Thomas (2015) who reported positive effect of different kind of computer assisted Computer based collaborative learning modes and Web-quest) on students' academic achievement. These studies were conduct at secondary school level using quasi experimental similar to the present study school setting and methodology.

The present study finding is also similar to the findings of Bahadur and Boodun (2013) who reported that Students taught using non-digital technology were able to learn and understand the different concepts related to water. The finding of the present study is in line with Carter, Greenberg and Walker (2016) who found that there was statistically significant difference in the attitude of students toward Trigonometry when taught using Linear PowerPoint and Non-digital technology. This finding is contrary to Falode, Ojoye, Ilobeneke, Falode (2016), Liu and Chen (2014), Gambari, Gbodi, Olakanmi, Abalaka (2016) who reported positive effect of digital instructional package on student's interest, attitude and motivation. This shows that Linear PowerPoint is capable of developing positive attitude in students toward Trigonometry.

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Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, the researchers came to the conclusion that using of digital tools, like Linear PowerPoint to teach Trigonometry has educational benefits. However, linear PowerPoint packages is more effective than non-digital technology because it improved students' academic performance in Mathematics particularly Trigonometry. This suggests that learners' cognitive behavior will improve when Linear PowerPoint is used to teach Trigonometry.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendation were made:

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1. Linear PowerPoint Instructional packages should be encouraged in schools for teaching Trigonometry.
2. Linear PowerPoint instructional Package was also found to be effective in teaching Trigonometry compared to non-digital technology of chalkboard. Teachers should use Linear PowerPoint Instructional package if they could not develop nor adapt Interactive PowerPoint instructional packages.
3. Concerned NGOs and Government bodies should provide adequate computer facilities that can enhance integration of Linear PowerPoint packages in teaching and learning of Trigonometry in Katsina education zone of Katsina state.

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